

Australian Vocabularies 2022 Workshop - Invited Event

16-18 November 2022, Australian National University, Canberra
(Following Australian Vocabularies Symposium 2022, 14-15 November)

DAY 1: Wednesday

Context Setting and Mapping the Current Landscape: Domain and Generic Vocabularies, Infrastructures, Relevant Documents and Communities	
Time	Item
10:00	Session 1: Opening <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Workshop plan - Steve McEachern (10min)2. Acknowledgement of country - Simon3. Introductions - Kheeran Dharmawardena (20min)
10:30	Session 2A: Context setting: Adrian Burton (slides) What are the next generation vocabulary requirements in Australia and what are the key strategies, roadmaps, direction setting and guiding documents that shape these requirements? <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Who is doing what and where?• What are the gaps in the existing overall system?• What are the overlaps/duplications?• What do we need, and who will provide what?
11:00	Break 1 (Coffee)
11:15	Session 2B: Context setting Andrew Hancock (slides)
11:40	Session 3: Mapping the landscape of Vocabularies <i>Form: Thematic breakout groups</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Review responses to questions posed at eResearch BOF and the Vocabulary Symposium2. Review vocabularies identified during Symposium: are there<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. Critical ones missing?b. Multiple versions of important vocabularies?3. Where are Australians utilising International Vocabulary resources?4. When should we have local, national vs international
12:30	Lunch

13:30	<p>Session 4: Report back on the Mapping the Landscape of Vocabularies <i>Form: Thematic breakout groups</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the key insights from the questions posed at eResearch and at the symposium? 2. Were there any major vocabularies identified that are missing from the Australian Vocabulary Ecosystem? 3. How does each thematic group prioritise when to use local vs national vs international vocabularies and services? Is there consensus?
14:00	<p>Session 5: Mapping the landscape of vocabulary Infrastructures <i>Form: Thematic breakout groups</i></p> <p>Vocabulary Infrastructures: some questions to consider:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How many vocabulary repositories are there - how many of their assets are FAIR? Known repositories include: RVA, Geoscience Australia, BoM, TERN, Department of Finance, ABS, AIHW (Meteor), Archives, GSQ, ????? 2. How many portals are there - are they FAIR? Known portals include: RVA, Ontoserver, GSQ, GA, TERN, HASS, National Archives, ABS, National Library, ABIS? 3. How many vocabulary aggregators are there in Australia? Known aggregators include RVA 4. How many systems are there to edit/manage vocabularies? What is their stability/sustainability? Known resources include RVA/PoolParty, Excel/SKOS-Play!, Excel/VocPrez, RDF tools (TopBraid, Protege) 5. What are the connections of any of these efforts with international equivalents? 6. What gaps we may have compared to international infrastructures?
15:30	<p>Session 6: Report back from Session 5 Plenary discussion to report back Mapping the Landscape of existing and missing Vocabulary Infrastructures in thematic areas.</p>
15:30	Break 3 (Coffee)
TO BE CONFIRMED	<p>Session 7: Moving Forward: Existing Guiding Documents and Communities that can influence our vision and roadmap <i>Form: Facilitator led group activity</i></p> <p>A review of known documents that can influence our Vision and roadmap as well as communities of practice that are also working</p>

	<p>on vocabularies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Forward Strategies and Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. CODATA Decadal Plan on Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges; b. 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap including the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy 2022 Guidelines c. Academies including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Australian Learned Academies Data Interworking Network Project (ALADIN) and the 5 reports on Australia’s Data-enabled research future ii. Australian Academy of Science Advancing data-intensive research in Australia d. UN Sustainable Development Goals e. Australian Government Documents: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Australian Data Strategy; ii. Commonwealth DATA legislation iii. ONDC implementation f. Australian Code For the Responsible Conduct of Research, in particular the Guide to the Management of data and information in research 2) Current planning documents in Australia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. RVA review and RVA Roadmap 2019-2024 3) Communities of Practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Australian Vocabulary Special Interest Group (AVSIG) b. AGLDWG (Australian Government Linked Data Working Group) c. Research Data Alliance (RDA) Vocabulary Services Interest Group d. Earth Systems Information Partners (ESIP) Semantic Harmonisation Committee <p>These are the known documents/communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does the audience know of any other documents that could either <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Inspire the roadmap b. Constrain the roadmap 2. Are there any other Communities of Practice we could ask to join in?
16:15	<p>Session 8: Outline a vision <i>Form: Facilitator let group activity</i></p> <p>Participants start to outline a visions statement</p>
16:30	<p>Close - Day end for participants</p>

16:30 - organisers	Organisers discussion TODO: 1. Decide breakout group members for day 2. 2. Upload day's content on to Miro board
17:00	Day end for all

DAY 2: Thursday

Guidance and Governance of cross domain vocabularies	
Time	Item
10:00 - plenary	<p>Session 9: Moving Forward: Existing Guiding Documents and Communities that can influence our vision and roadmap <i>Form: Facilitator led group activity</i></p> <p>A review of known documents that may influence our Vision and roadmap as well as communities of practice that are also working on vocabularies (slides)</p> <p>1) Forward Strategies and Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap including the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy 2022 Guidelines b. CODATA Decadal Plan on Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges: c. UN Sustainable Development Goals d. Academies including: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Australian Learned Academies Data Interworking Network Project (ALADIN) and the 5 reports on Australia's Data-enabled research future ii. Australian Academy of Science Advancing data-intensive research in Australia e. Australian Code For the Responsible Conduct of Research, in particular the Guide to the Management of data and information in research f. Australian Government Documents: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Australian Data Strategy; ii. Commonwealth DATA legislation iii. ONDC implementation <p>2) Current planning documents in Australia</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. RVA review and RVA Roadmap 2019-2024 <p>3) Communities of Practice</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Australian Vocabulary Special Interest Group (AVSIG) b. AGLDWG (Australian Government Linked Data Working Group) c. Research Data Alliance (RDA) Vocabulary Services Interest Group d. Earth Systems Information Partners (ESIP) Semantic Harmonisation Committee <p>These are the known documents/communities:</p>

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10:45	<p>Session 10: Cross-domain scenario Part 1 We need to provide advice on what are the environmental, economic and social determinants of a new disease? (e.g., mapping the spread of a new disease in northern Australia) - identify the target vocabularies we need to have access to? (slides)</p> <p>Breakout groups made up of mixtures of at least two people each thematic area from HASS, People, Planet, Generic and also a mix of skills, technical and domain to Identify:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Which target vocabularies are required to assist in this scenario? 2) What are the main barriers to linking these across infrastructures - are they domain, technical, sector, social or governance?
11:45	Break 1 (Coffee)
12:00	<p>Session 11: Cross-domain scenario Part 2 Report back with focus on Vocabularies and Barriers <i>Form: Breakout groups report back + plenary discussion</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Which are the critical datasets that we need? What are their vocabularies? 2) What were the main barriers to linking datasets across infrastructures? <p>Structured period for each of the breakout groups to hear what was considered in the other groups and reflect on and amend what they have considered.</p> <p>Joint discussions How do we address the barriers to interdisciplinary integration of vocabularies in Australia?</p>
12:30	<p>Session 12: Cross-domain scenario Part 3: Focus on vocabularies across domains and cross-domain vocabularies <i>Form: Breakout groups</i></p> <p>How may targeted vocabularies be related to each other?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Which vocabularies are required across multiple domains? (e.g., colour, Units of Measure, location, geographical boundaries, ???) 2. Which vocabularies are domain-specific but are needed by

	other (specialist domain Vocabularies that need to be referenced by other domains)
13:00	Break 2 (Lunch)
13:30	<p>Session 13: Choosing which Domain vocabularies to Trust Thematic breakout groups (HASS, Planet, People, Generic)</p> <p>Two questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can you provide online guidance for selecting a vocabulary if you are not from that domain? 2. What do we do with multiple copies of similar vocabularies, particularly those that are direct reproductions/web scrapes of existing vocabularies?
15:00	Break 3 (Coffee)
15:15	<p>Session 14: Bringing it together The management and use of vocabularies and effective use of services and tools available in the ecosystem for cross-domain data integration.</p>
15:45 - plenary	<p>Session 15: Refine a vision</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Refine vision statement from Day 1 2. Outline a skeleton for a roadmap for vocabularies and semantic resources in Australia

DAY 3: Friday, half-day

The Path Forward	
Time	Item
10:00	Session 16: Recap A recap of day 1 and 2 ecosystem and solution mapping. Could cross-domain scenarios be supported?
10:30	Session 17: Roadmap (and finalise vision statement if necessary) Start defining building blocks of the roadmap
11:30	Break 1 (coffee)
11:45	Session 18: Continuing the Roadmap Firming up the roadmap for vocabularies and semantic resources in Australia and getting flesh on the skeleton:
13:00	Session 19: Moving forward and next steps <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishing the “Australian Vocabularies Advocacy Group” 2. Next steps from here <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What is the target completion date b. Who will publish the road map c. Means of communication between members?
13:15	Session 20: Closing of workshop Steve
13:30	Lunch & end